

STUDIES IN VITAMIN-C OXIDATION. PART II. INFLUENCE OF VARIOUS SUBSTANCES OCCURRING IN PLANT AND ANIMAL TISSUES ON THE CATALYTIC OXIDATION OF VITAMIN-C.

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A study has been made of the influence of various substances on the catalytic oxidation of vitamin-C by Cu. Among the substances investigated, oxalic acid, xanthine, uric acid, theophylline, creatinine, antipyrine and albumin exert powerful protective action, while tartaric, citric, malic, maleic, malonic, tannic and aspartic acids, glycine, alanine, asparagine, histamine and pyrogallol exert slight protection against the oxidation of the vitamin. Creatine, succinic acid and other compounds investigated exert no protection. The various possible mechanisms underlying the action of these substances on vitamin-C oxidation are discussed.

In a recent note (Giri and Krishnamurthy, *Nature*, 1940, 146, 99) and in the previous part of this series (Krishnamurthy and Giri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 7) evidence was given which indicated the presence of protective factors in vegetables, which inhibit the catalytic oxidation of vitamin-C by Cu⁺⁺. Attempts to identify the factors were partly successful and tartaric acid was found to be present in the extract exhibiting the protective action. In addition to tartaric acid there may be many more protective constituents in plants, which have not so far been identified. The only substances, which are known to exert protective action on vitamin-C oxidation, and which also occur in plant and animal tissues, are glutathione (Hopkins and Morgan, *Biochem. J.*, 1936, 30, 1446), cysteine, cystine, pyrophosphate (Giri, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1937, 25, 443; *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1937, 245, 185; Krishnamurthy and Giri, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1941, 29, 71), cyanide, sulphuretted hydrogen, chlorophyll and amino-acids (Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 1; Mystkowski and Lasocka, *Biochem. J.*, 1939, 33, 1460). It was, therefore, thought that a study of the effect of various other substances, which commonly occur in plant and animal tissues, may serve to throw further light on the nature of the protective factors. The present paper deals with the influence of about sixty substances on the catalytic oxidation of vitamin-C. Several new substances have now been discovered, which exert powerful inhibiting action on the catalytic oxidation of the vitamin by Cu⁺⁺.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The rate of oxidation of vitamin-C was determined as described in

the previous paper (*loc. cit.*). Glass-distilled water and analytically pure chemicals were used in the experiments.

The reaction mixture contained 9 c.c. of *M*/₅-acetic acid-acetate buffer (*pH* 5.6); 1 c.c. of copper sulphate solution containing 0.07 mg. of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and 5 c.c. of the solution containing the substance, whose action on the oxidation of the vitamin is to be determined, were added. The total volume of the reaction mixture was made up to 20 c.c. The flasks containing the reaction mixtures were kept at 37° in an electrically controlled thermostat. After the experimental solutions attained the temperature of the thermostat, 5 c.c. of vitamin-C solution containing 5 mg. of the vitamin were added, and immediately after shaking the contents of the flask, 2 c.c. of the reaction mixture were pipetted out into a beaker containing 1 c.c. of glacial acetic acid, and titrated with the indophenol dye. The titre value, thus obtained, represents the initial value for vitamin-C. At stated intervals 2 c.c. of the reaction mixture were pipetted out and similarly titrated.

All determinations of the rates of oxidation have been made with the same amount of Cu^{++} and with the same concentration of vitamin-C. The results are, therefore, comparable, and the relative effect of the substances on vitamin-C oxidation is clearly shown.

In Table I is given the percentage of inhibition (degree of protection) exerted by each substance against the oxidation of the vitamin by Cu^{++} . The percentage of inhibition (degree of protection) is calculated according to the formula given by Giri and Shourie (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1940, 27, 685).

The percentage of inhibition (degree of protection) exerted by the substance against the catalytic oxidation of vitamin-C by Cu^{++} is expressed as percentage inhibition $\equiv$

$$100 \left(1 - \frac{\text{Amt. of vitamin-C destroyed in presence of the subst. in 1 hr. at } 37^\circ}{\text{Amt. of vitamin-C destroyed in absence of the subst. in 1 hr. at } 37^\circ} \right)$$

Thus, when there is complete protection without any oxidation of the vitamin, the percentage inhibition is 100.

TABLE I.

Percentage of inhibition (degree of protection) of various substances on the catalytic oxidation of vitamin-C by Cu^{++} .

Substance.	Conc. refers to the concentration of the reacting mixture.		Substance.	Conc. refers to the concentration of the reacting mixture.	
	Conc.	% Inhibition		Conc.	% Inhibition.
Carboxylic acids.					
Formic acid	<i>M</i> / ₅₀	0	Fumaric acid	<i>M</i> / ₅₀	11
Benzoic acid	"	0	Phthalic acid	<i>M</i> / ₇₅	0
Oxalic acid	"	82	Nicotinic acid	0.3%	0
Succinic acid	"	0	Cinnamic acid	<i>M</i> / ₅₀	0
Maleic acid	"	11			

TABLE I (contd.).

Hydroxy compounds.					
Substance.	Conc.	% Inhibition.	Substance.	Conc.	% Inhibition.
Alcohol	M/50	0	Hydroquinone	M/50	0
Glycol	"	0	Pyrogallol	"	34
Glycerol	"	0	Phloroglucinol	"	0
Phenol	"	0	α -Naphthol	0.01%	0
Catechol	"	0	β -Naphthol	0.02%	0
Resorcinol	"	0	Xanthidrol	0.01%	0
Hydroxy-carboxylic acids.					
Tartaric acid	M/50	41	Malic acid	M/50	25
Citric acid	"	36	Salicylic acid	"	0
Lactic acid	"	10	Tannic acid	"	41
Malonic acid	"	23	Gallic acid	"	0
Amino compounds.					
Urea	M/50	0	Histamine	0.5%	30
Glycine	"	13	Valine	M/50	23
Creatine	"	0	Guanidine carbonate	0.5%	17
Alanine	"	20	Aspartic acid	M/50	25
Asparagine	"	36	Choline chloride	"	19
Purines.					
Xanthine	0.05%	80	Uric acid	0.0012%	75
Caffeine	0.1%	0	Theophylline	0.06%	92
Compounds having NH-CO group.					
Hippuric acid	0.2%	11	Semicarbazide hydrochloride	M/50	0
Antipyrine	M/50	83	Veronal	M/75	0
Acetanilide	"	0	Creatinine	M/50	96
Miscellaneous substances.					
Digitalis	0.5%	0	Glycogen	0.5%	0
Strophanthin	"	0	Lecithin (egg)	0.2%	31
Saponin	"	21	Fructose	M/50	0
Albumin (egg)	"	84	Peptone	0.5%	37
			Tyrosine	0.1%	"

DISCUSSION.

A significant finding of the present study is the recognition of a number of new substances, which exert powerful inhibiting action on the catalytic oxidation of vitamin-C by Cu^{++} . These substances are widely distributed in plant and animal tissues, and they are of great importance from the point of view of their relationship to the protective action of tissues on the vitamin.

Among the carboxylic acids investigated, oxalic, tartaric, citric, malonic, malic, maleic, fumaric and tannic acids exert protective action, while succinic and other acids have no effect on the oxidation. Oxalic acid exerts the greatest protection of all the acids investigated. The powerful protective action of oxalic acid against the catalytic oxidation of the vitamin possesses an interesting feature and it reveals an important function of oxalic acid in plant tissues. This finding is of great importance in view of the fact that oxalic acid occurs in the tissues of many species belonging to the higher green plants. One of the protective constituents present in *amaranth* (Krishnamurthy and Giri, *loc. cit.*) may be oxalic acid, which is known to occur in the leaves of the plant. It may be mentioned here that Watanabe (*J. Soc. Trop. Agr. Taihoku Imp. Univ.*, 1937, 8, 381; 9, 162) has already shown that oxalic acid exerts stabilising action on vitamin-C, and he has used a mixture of oxalic and metaphosphoric acid for the extraction and stabilisation of vitamin-C from vegetables. In a later communication (*ibid.*, 1937, 9, 368) he has also shown that oxalic acid retards the oxidation of vitamin-C by charcoal.

Among the hydroxy compounds, only pyrogallol exerts slight protection against the oxidation of the vitamin. It is interesting to know that hydroquinone, resorcinol and salicylic acid, which are known as antioxidants, do not exert any influence on the vitamin.

The results obtained on the influence of purines, creatinine, and creatine on vitamin-C oxidation are of great interest. The purines are with difficulty soluble in water, but the concentrations taken sufficed to exert a definite inhibiting action on the oxidation. Xanthine, uric acid and theophylline exert strong protective action against the oxidation of the vitamin (70-98% inhibition), while caffeine does not exert any influence on the vitamin.

An interesting difference between creatine and creatinine, the two important constituents of the muscle, is revealed by their influence on vitamin-C oxidation. Although creatine has no influence on the oxidation, creatinine, which is the anhydride of creatine, is found to exert powerful protection against the catalytic oxidation of the vitamin.

As regards the nature of the protection exerted by some of the substances investigated, several possible mechanisms may be suggested, namely,

(1) The substance may form a complex with Cu^{++} , thereby preventing the catalytic action of the ionised Cu on vitamin-C. Citric, tartaric, oxalic and other acids may exert their action in this manner.

(2) The substance may function as hydrogen donator, thereby reducing the oxidised vitamin (dehydroascorbic acid) back to reduced vitamin, and this reduction, being much faster than the oxidation, the substance may function as a protector.

(3) The substance may form a compound with vitamin-C, which is more stable and less rapidly oxidised by Cu^{++} than the free vitamin.

However, little is known regarding the precise mechanism involved in each case. It may, however, be mentioned here that some of the substances like citric acid and the amino-acids are known to form complexes with Cu^{++} , and the protective action exerted by these substances may be attributed to this cause.

From the foregoing account it is likely that there exist certain structural chemical requirements with respect to the purines as inhibitors of vitamin-C oxidation, probably the existence of a free imino grouping in the purines *e.g.*: xanthine, uric acid, and theophylline. The *N*-substituted purine caffeine does not exert any inhibition even at such a high concentration as 0.1%, while those purines, whose γ -imino-N is not substituted *e.g.*, xanthine, uric and theophylline, exert strong inhibition on the oxidation of the vitamin.

It would be premature to base any wide conclusions upon the limited findings of the work here described.

The authors wish to acknowledge with thanks the facilities granted by Major J. F. Shepherd for carrying out the above investigations in the Andhra Medical College. The authors' thanks are also due to Dr. G. Gopalarao for discussion.

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Received November 4, 1940.